

Mapping a new gene for resistance to bacterial blight using RFLP markers

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Bacterial blight (BB) of rice, caused by *Xanthomonas oryzae* pv. *oryzae* (Ishiyama) Dye, is prevalent throughout Asia. Some resistant cultivars were identified from 6,184 Yunnan local varieties by using 10 BB strains from China, Philippines, and Japan. Japonica Zha-Chang-Long (ZCL) was resistant to all BB strains tested (Chen et al 1990). A dominant gene controlled the resistance of ZCL to BB strain PXO61 and was nonallelic to *Xa1*, *Xa2*, *Xa3*, and *Xa14* (Xie et al 1990).

To identify this resistance gene, we mapped it based on restriction fragment length polymorphism (RFLP) markers by using bulked extremes and susceptible class analysis (Michelmore et al 1991, Zhang et al 1994). The mapping population was the F_2 of the cross between ZCL and Zhen-Zhui-Ai which is an indica susceptible to all BB strains. Equal amounts of DNA of 30 extremely resistant F_2 plants were mixed to make a resistant bulk. Equal amounts of DNA of 42 extremely susceptible plants (lesion length was longer than 9 cm) were mixed to make a susceptible bulk. The DNA samples of two parents and two bulks were digested with six enzymes (*Bam*HI, *Dra*I, *Eco*RI, *Eco*RV, *Hind*III, and *Xba*I) and were assayed for RFLP with 99 clone fragments provided by S. D. Tanksley and T. Sasaki.

Of 99 probes, 35 (35.4%) were polymorphic between the combined parents tested and covered about 855 cM of the rice genome, which was about 58% of Cornell's RFLP linkage map length (Causse et al 1994). The ability to verify polymorphism using genomic clones was higher (44.1%) than that using cDNA clones (15.6%). Twenty-eight polymorphic probes had intensity bands similar to those of their parents in resistant bulk and susceptible bulk.

Performance of RFLP marker of plants in the susceptible population.

Probe	Type of band ^a				p (%) ^b	Genetic map distance (cM)
	1	2	3	Total		
R543	1	2	39	42	4.8 ± 2.3	4.8 ± 2.3
G181	1	5	36	42	8.3 ± 3.0	8.4 ± 3.0
RZ536	1	7	34	42	10.7 ± 3.4	10.9 ± 3.4
C950	1	7	34	42	10.7 ± 3.4	10.9 ± 3.4
G389	2	8	32	42	14.3 ± 3.8	14.7 ± 3.8
RG1109	3	17	22	42	27.4 ± 4.9	30.8 ± 4.9
G4001	3	17	22	42	27.4 ± 4.9	30.8 ± 4.9

^a1 = no. of plants with resistant parent band. 2 = no. of plants with two parent bands. 3 = no. of plants with susceptible parent band. ^bRecombination frequencies between markers and the gene for resistance to BB.

The locus of the gene for resistance to bacterial blight in Yunnan rice variety Zha-Chang-Long on RFLP linkage 11 of rice.

Seven polymorphic probes were mainly susceptible parent bands in susceptible bulk. The resistance gene of ZCL was linked to the chromosome region of these seven probes on chromosome 11. Distances between the resistance gene of ZCL and the probes were determined (see table). The resistance gene of ZCL was located on the top of chromosome 11 (see

figure). The locus of this resistance gene was different from the loci of resistance genes previously mapped on this chromosome. A new dominant resistance gene to BB exists in Yunnan rice variety ZCL.

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